

EMD Workshop Summary

“Algae Solutions for a Thriving Blue Economy”

Moderated by **Adrien Vincent**, the workshop brought together the EU-funded projects **SeaMark**, **REALM** and **CIRCALGAE** to showcase the latest breakthroughs from the projects, and how they promote sustainability, scale and competitiveness of the blue economy.

More than 650 million euro has gone into the algae sector in funding in the past years, and when the projects were funded four years ago, this was a strong signal of the commission´s acknowledgement of the sector´s importance.

Evdokia Achilleos, Head of Sector in Unit B3 at the European Research Executive Agency (REA), welcomed the audience by highlighting that these efforts are highly aligned with a shared mission of unlocking the potential of algae for a thriving blue European bioeconomy. However, she also stressed that funding alone is not enough for success of projects. Evidence based policy is key and collective actions amplify the outcome and speeds up innovation. The Ocean pact and the new Bioeconomy strategy include boosting the competitiveness of the blue bioeconomy and support prioritisation of aquatic biomass. And, as the sector matures, there is a growing need for high quality, society ready outcomes, clear evidence to support market uptake and effective strategies to bridge the gap between research and commercialization.

The three projects presented their **key outcomes**, results and **experienced barriers** to then discuss three cross cutting themes identified as needs; accelerating biorefinery circularity, valuing algae ecosystem services and navigating algae scale-up costs.

Amparo Jiménez Quero presented the **CIRCALGAE project** that aims to develop circular algae biorefineries that valorise algae biomass and side streams into sustainable products for food, feed, and cosmetics applications. The project has successfully developed three integrated biorefinery schemes and advanced 12 demonstrators to TRL 7 through green extraction, fractionation, and formulation strategies. Key barriers remain related to process scale-up, regulatory frameworks, biomass variability, and the economic feasibility of large-scale deployment. The main takeaway is that integrated algae biorefineries can significantly strengthen the circular bioeconomy, but wider industrial implementation will depend on overcoming technical and regulatory challenges.

Ólavur Gregersen presented the **SeaMark findings**, highlighting the high technology readiness level achieved for both ocean-based and land-based cultivation of *Saccharina* and *Ulva*. The protocols, scientific functional validations, and prototypes developed

within SeaMark are now ready for exploitation, with 10 key exploitable results (KERs) identified.

Reflecting on the project, biostimulants should have been included from the outset among the other 12 products. Biostimulant products derived from cultivated seaweed are expected to play a leading role in market development and to enable industry scaling, while addressing a key EU challenge of reducing fertiliser use in agriculture.

However, regulatory barriers remain a significant bottleneck. For example, constraints affecting fucoidan-based health products and biostimulants derived from cultivated seaweed are limiting market access, forcing companies to operate outside Europe, making it difficult to attract investment. A systematic regulatory shift is therefore needed to unlock the full potential of algae-based solutions in Europe.

Mariana Carneiro presented the **REALM project** that aims to boost sustainable microalgae production through a decentralized and circular model that utilises nutrient-rich drain water from agriculture to cultivate low-cost biomass. Key opportunities lie in the creation of value from waste, while boosting the competitiveness and sustainability of the algae and agriculture sectors. However, scaling this system is currently hindered by several risks such as that of biological contamination and restrictive legislative barriers preventing the deployment of algae facilities on agricultural land. Consequently, the commercial viability and future replication of these sustainable algae processes will fundamentally depend on resolving these technical bottlenecks and modernising agricultural zoning policies.

The discussions largely revolved around the need for systematic change in the context of the European algae sector. The technology and methodologies for cultivation and refinery are mature enough to scale, and there is data available to support implementation of ecosystem service valorisation schemes.

We have proof that algae can play a key role in a circular and sustainable biomass production industry in Europe and offer important societal benefits as well as sustainability pathways for other industries. Examples are using algae-derived biostimulants in agriculture can reduce the need of chemical fertilizers, and utilising wastewater as a medium for growing algae, recirculating “waste” to produce biomass. However, the regulatory and market environment is currently not favouring the use and production of algae. Examples involve novel food hurdles, side-stream or “waste” utilisation regulation.

For valorisation of sustainability aspects, the main need is harmonisation of LCA schemes between different feedstocks, to reliably quantify environmental effects of algae-based products and its land-counterparts. The evidence base is there, and now it must be agreed across stakeholders to be able to put algae in the societal context in

which it belongs, and its potential integration with other industries and sustainability policy.

Further, the panel stressed the importance of scaling for cost efficiency in a costly sector. Production is currently expensive, creating a higher price of biomass in comparison to global market price. Scaling allows for technology investments reducing production costs through reduction of labour needs, ability to handle more biomass, and digitalisation optimising the full value chain. This also applies on the product development side as the industry today faces high costs associated with verifying claims and certifications enabling market entry. This creates unfair competition dynamics in comparison to alternatives from outside EU, where production is cheaper and market entry easier.

During the panel discussion, the audience was engaged in providing their own solutions for each topic, and their prioritisation of the gathered solutions was collected at the end. This resulted in a total of twenty-seven action points called for to support the scaling of the European algae industry. These were then prioritised by voting on the top three most important actions to unlock its potential. The most actionable solutions identified revolved around enabling and diversifying sales and products in the EU, and providing algae value streams the opportunity to fairly compete with other products as well as non-EU countries:

- Enable sales in EU with fast product registration and include new feedstocks.
- Identify valuable and scalable products.
- Reduce unfair competition between EU and non-EU companies.

Other important actions identified revolved around reducing production costs and finding pathways to allow for valorisation of ecosystem services or sustainability provisions from algae cultivation.

The core message from the projects and discussions are that the sector has reached a new level of maturity, and the results of the projects are very valuable for the tomorrow of the sector. Today, we know much more about how to successfully get into the market. The opportunities, needs and barriers are uncovered, and this is what should be focused on to progress into a prosperous algae industry in Europe. The biomass, the products and the companies are there, and the sector will be a large contributor to the European bioeconomy, but still the market and legislation have to adapt. To prevent us from having to reinvent the wheel and instead effectively use available funding to improve it, it is very important that we use the current knowledge, data and momentum to create a foundation to keep growing from, based in research and information relevant and useful for the industry. Regulations today are made for the biomass it was created for, and we need policy innovation to allow algae to take the place it deserves.

Appendix 1

Detailed discussion summary

On the topic of **biorefinery circularity**, Amparo Jiménez Quero shared the experiences from CIRCALGAE; that a big part of biomass is not used when producing other products than for example food. The project also proved you can get other types of ingredients from these side streams, but a main challenge is that once you have generated a side stream it is hard to realise the value chain and bring it to the market, due to it being labelled as “waste”. There is a lot of space to increase the use of algae and also the efficiency in the conversion of biomass to multiple products. Ólavur Gregersen raised the issue of cost efficiency in the full value chain as a driver for circularity. Since cultivated seaweed comes with high costs, we need to identify all possible revenues to be able to justify scaling. Mariana Carneiro raised the work done by REALM to overcome technological barriers of having large quantities of water to process in microalgae production. Using automation coupled with wastewater as nutrient and water source gets costs down and increases the circularity of the process. Regarding regulations, it was highlighted that the labelling of biomass in Europe is an issue, both in terms of possibilities to use “waste” for different applications, but also the general problem of algae classification and Novel Food regulation hurdles.

Audience input on what is needed to accelerate biorefinery circularity:

- To select a defined and scaled algae market and work towards making the market more profitable
- Provide market subsidies
- Ease up some regulatory constraints such as Novel Food application.
- The cost of the basic biomass must still be reduced significantly.
- Enable sales in EU with fast product registration and include new feedstocks.
- To develop the market.
- Long term takeoff agreements with the big companies to de-risk the cost of building processing plants.
- Energetically efficient systems.
- To select a defined and scaled algae market and work towards making the market more profitable.
- Identify valuable and scalable products.

The second topic raised the potential of algae as a **sustainable biomass with environmental benefits, though quantifying and monetizing its benefits remains difficult**. Mariana Carneiro called to monetize the service of algae to absorb pollution from different industries. This does not have to be attractive for the industries themselves, but for investments, and coupled with strict LCAs to clearly quantify the service provided and the value it gives. Carbon has a lot of regulatory frameworks, but similar mechanisms can be explored for other pollutants like nitrogen and phosphorous.

Ólavur Gregersen stressed this is a key opportunity for the industry that must be realised, using biostimulants as an example. Algae cultivation does not only provide services during cultivation but can also help avoid additional input from use of fertilisers in agriculture. This should be used as a “carrot on the stick” for the polluters to also support the industry, but we need policy to support this reform. We currently have a lot of data, but we need to see the system change. Amparo Jiménez Quero added the dimension of difficulty in quantification of the effects as algae change over time and do not have the same composition. This is also important to realise when talking about scaling production, as we are expecting to do.

Audience input on **how we value algae ecosystem services:**

- No direct money for them but link them to financing.
- Allow to generate and sell credits for CO₂, nitrogen, phosphorous, etc.
- Have more standardized protocols for monitoring and quantification of the different ecosystem services.
- For ocean cultivation - start with nutrient credits to support the industry in scaling.
- CRCF regulation should include algae.
- Integrate them to sustainable finance frameworks to mobilize capital for scale rather than additional value per tonne biomass.
- Develop standardized metrics across the food (or other) system.
- Showcasing.
- Integrating them as priorities when allocating funding.
- Scaling up.

The last question discussed by the panel was on how to **tackle the high costs of cultivation**. The costs of production in Europe are high, and hence the market price is higher. Products also have added costs of certifications necessary to enter the market. Novel food regulation is a major bottle neck, and the possibility of imported biomass being re-labelled in EU creates unfair competitiveness, and major difficulties for the European industries to realise their place. Cascading refinery opens the possibility to generate multiple value streams from biomass, and the projects have shown it to work. Mariana Carneiro also mentioned the use of waste streams to reduce some of the costs, but reinforced the need of establishing safety frameworks, in addition to an increased automation of the process. This will also be a key component for the companies to tackle the high production costs and optimised revenue creation. Ólavur Gregersen further raised the importance of continuing genetic and breeding research to also optimise biomass production at the start, and that it is not only technological innovation that can lower production costs.

How to navigate algae scale-up costs?

- Analyse KPI and leverage detected potential.

- Include the entire horizontal B2B value chain in the cost assessment and prioritize competitive solutions.
- Key differences between micro and macro algae, wild harvest vs cultivated.
- Total digitalisation of the entire value chain and administrative processes.
- A lot depends on whether it is for micro or macro algae scale up.
- Selective breeding, focus on one main product driver, de-risk finances for scaling.
- Improve productivity.
- Diverting harmful subsidies to invest in algae production.

Optional additional takes:

- More honest reflection on failures and lessons learned in projects is valuable for the field to progress. Something that should be encouraged that projects to more often?
- A specific take: Policy on how to classify algae. Are they aquaculture or both aquaculture and agricultural crops? Which then determines where one can cultivate microalgae as a land may only have the regulatory permit to produce agricultural crops
- Biological contamination is an underfunded technical bottleneck. While in many aspects speakers said that a lot of knowledge exists and now regulation is a major obstacle, biological contamination was mentioned in terms of more research being needed.
- More concretely point out the role of public subsidies in reinforcing unsustainable systems or the other way around how subsidies could be tied to regenerative practices; making the use of regenerative practices a requisite to get subsidies. It is listed in the audience suggestions and rankings. The summary text could perhaps include a take on it as well if space allows

Appendix 2

Slido results - Results from the participant voting on most relevant action point:

Solution Blue: what is needed to accelerate biorefinery circularity, red: navigate algae scale-up costs, green: how we value algae ecosystem services	Total votes	Ranking		
		#1	#2	#3
Enable sales in EU with fast product registration and include new feedstocks	16	16		
Identify valuable and scalable products	12	7	5	
Reducing unfair competition between EU and non-EU companies	10	1		9
The cost of the basic biomass must still be reduced significantly	9	1	8	
Ease up some regulatory constraints such as Novel Food application	8	1	4	3
Integrating ecosystem services as priorities when allocating funding	5	2		3
Integrating ecosystem services to sustainable finance frameworks to mobilise capital for scale rather than additional value per tonne biomass	4	1	3	
Diverting harmful subsidies to invest in algae production	3			3
Harmonisation of LCA's and developing standardised metrics across systems	3		2	1
Selective breeding, focus on one main product driver, de-risk finances for scaling	2		1	1
Implementing the knowledge and science that has been developed over the last few years	2	1		1
Total digitalisation of the entire value chain and administrative processes	2			2
Long term takeoff agreements with the big companies to de-risk the cost of building processing plants	2		1	1
Allowing to generate and sell credits for CO2, nitrogen, phosphorous, etc	1		1	
Including the entire horizontal B2B value chain in the cost assessment and prioritising competitive solutions	1			1

Appendix 3

Slido results - Description of workshop participants:

What is your primary role in the blue economy?	Policymaker / Regulator	0
	Scientist / Researcher	15
	Industry Expert / Entrepreneur	7
	NGO / Civil Society Representative	5
	Other	6
What is your main motivation for attending this specific workshop?	Influencing EU policy and identifying actionable points	12
	Learning about breakthrough project results	9
	Networking for future industry-research collaboration	17
	Other	1
What actionable outcome do you most want to take away from this interactive session?	A clear list of policy adjustments to forward to the European Commission	12
	Defined next steps based on the project presentations	5
	Identification of key enablers to unlock algae innovation	24
How should the European Commission primarily use the feedback we generate today?	To shape and fund future Horizon Europe calls	8
	To adjust existing regulatory restrictions	25
	To support the implementation of the European Ocean Pact	6